

A Framework for Technology Radar Development: A Literature-Based and Project-Driven Approach

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of a Technology Radar framework developed in the context of the AI-DAPT project. Technology Radars are widely used to monitor emerging technologies, yet existing approaches often differ substantially in methodology, update mechanisms, and integration of evidence sources. To address this challenge, the paper derives framework requirements through a structured literature review and develops an AI-assisted, project-driven radar framework that combines scientific publications, industry-oriented sources, automated data processing, and expert validation.

The framework was implemented and applied within AI-DAPT, resulting in a publicly available Technology Radar comprising 127 technologies organized across four thematic quadrants and four maturity levels. Expert validation contributed 49 additional technologies and 51 technology reclassifications, demonstrating the complementary value of combining automated analysis with domain-specific expertise. The resulting framework provides a structured, transferable, and continuously evolving approach for technology monitoring and decision support in research and innovation projects.

Index Terms—Technology Radar, Artificial Intelligence, Innovation Management, Emerging Technologies, Decision Support Systems, Research and Technology Monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data-driven technologies is reshaping industrial, societal, and scientific domains at an unprecedented pace [1]–[3]. Within this dynamic landscape, large-scale research and innovation initiatives such as the AI-DAPT project - which will be used as a specific use case for the approach of this paper - operate at the intersection of multiple disciplines, including data-driven AI pipelines, ICT, human-in-the-loop, operational research and regulatory requirements (e.g., the AI Act). This setting is fur-

ther embedded in a broader ecosystem of European and global initiatives (e.g., AI-on-demand platforms, GAIA-X, ADRA), which collectively contribute to an increasingly complex and interconnected technology space. In such environments, systematically identifying, structuring, and monitoring emerging technologies and research trends becomes a critical capability to support the development of future solutions. Technology radars have therefore emerged as a widely adopted instrument to support strategic awareness and decision-making by providing structured overviews of technological developments from scientific, market, and application-oriented perspectives [4], [5].

Despite their widespread use, Technology Radars are often developed in heterogeneous ways [4], [6], lacking standardized methodologies and clear alignment with specific project needs, as discussed in Section II. This is particularly challenging in interdisciplinary research projects such as AI-DAPT, where technological developments must be continuously assessed across multiple domains and stakeholder perspectives. Existing approaches frequently emphasize either academic trend analysis or market-oriented scouting, but rarely integrate these dimensions in a coherent and operational manner [7]. Consequently, there is a need to identify and consolidate best practices for designing and implementing a Technology Radar that is both methodologically sound and tailored to the specific requirements of a complex, multi-domain research project. This gap motivates a systematic investigation of existing Technology Radar approaches as a foundation for deriving project-specific requirements.

Against this background, the objective of this paper is to present the development and application of an AI-DAPT-

specific Research and Technology Radar as a specific showcase on creating a coherent and efficient framework that generalizes design principles for Technology Radar development and demonstrates their application within the AI-DAPT project. The paper first conducts a structured literature review to analyze existing Technology Radar approaches and identify relevant design principles and best practices. Based on these insights, a set of requirements is derived to guide the development of a tailored radar framework that captures scientific, technological, and application perspectives, while also integrating external initiatives and patent analysis. Subsequently, the paper introduces the implemented radar framework and discusses its application within the AI-DAPT project. Finally, the effectiveness and practical value of the approach are evaluated, with reflections on its transferability to other research projects, domains, and contexts.

II. EXISTING THEORY AND RELATED WORK

To establish a robust foundation for the development of the proposed Technology Radar framework, a structured literature review was conducted to systematically identify, analyze, and synthesize existing contributions in the fields of Technology Radar, technology intelligence, and related foresight approaches [5], [7]. Given the interdisciplinary and partly fragmented nature of the topic, the review combines keyword-based database searches with citation chaining techniques to ensure both broadness and completeness of the identified literature. Particular emphasis was placed on identifying methodological contributions that explicitly address the design, implementation, or application of Technology Radar approaches, as well as complementary works that provide conceptual grounding within the broader context of technology intelligence and innovation management.

The literature review process follows a structured approach inspired by the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework, which provides standardized guidance for the transparent identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion of scientific studies [8].

Figure 1 shows a literature review that followed a structured multi-stage procedure to identify and analyze scientific contributions related to Technology Radar methodologies and adjacent concepts in technology intelligence and foresight. The review was designed to balance breadth and analytical depth, as the initial screening indicated that the number of publications explicitly addressing the Technology Radar as a methodological construct is comparatively limited, while a broader body of literature addresses related activities such as technology intelligence, technology scouting, technology foresight, and technology mapping. In the identification phase, a broad search strategy was applied using keyword combinations such as Technology Radar, technology and innovation radar, automated Technology Radar, and technology scouting radar. To capture adjacent but methodologically relevant studies, the search was extended with terms including technology intelligence, technology foresight, and technology mapping.

Fig. 1. PRISMA-inspired literature screening and selection workflow for technology radars

The search was conducted across major scientific publishers, while the final publication set is primarily represented by Elsevier/ScienceDirect, complemented by Wiley Online Library, BMJ, NASA-related technical sources, and additional scholarly indexing sources. This step resulted in 39 records considered potentially relevant on the basis of title matches, abstract matches, or citation chaining from core radar publications.

In the screening phase, all identified records were assessed based on title and, where accessible, abstract. Publications were excluded if they did not refer to the Technology Radar or a closely related construct in technology and innovation management, if they addressed unrelated radar domains, or if they lacked a scientific or methodological contribution. This first reduction step excluded 20 records, leaving 19 publications for full-text assessment.

In the eligibility phase, the remaining records were examined in full text wherever accessible. At this stage, the analysis focused on whether a publication contributed directly to the design, implementation, evaluation, or conceptual grounding of Technology Radar approaches. Additional inclusion criteria were methodological relevance, scientific rigor, and suitability for cross-paper comparison. Preference was given to peer-reviewed and recent publications, while seminal earlier works were retained where they formed the conceptual foundation of the field. During this step, 9 further records were excluded because they showed only peripheral relevance, lacked a

TABLE I
CORE AND EXTENSION PUBLICATIONS FOR TECHNOLOGY RADAR FRAMEWORK

Ref.	Author(s)	Title	Year	Type	Publisher
Core Technology Radar Publications					
[9]	Rohrbeck, R. et al.	The Value Contribution of Strategic Foresight: Insights from an Empirical Study of Large European Companies	2013	Journal Article	Elsevier
[10]	Rohrbeck, R.; Kum, M.	Corporate Foresight and Its Impact on Firm Performance: A Longitudinal Analysis	2018	Journal Article	Elsevier
[7]	Phaal, R.; Farrukh, C.; Probert, D.	Technology Roadmapping—A Planning Framework for Evolution and Revolution	2004	Journal Article	Elsevier
[11]	Rohrbeck, R.	Exploring value creation from corporate foresight activities	2012	Journal Article	Elsevier
[12]	Daim, T. et al.	Forecasting Emerging Technologies: Use of Bibliometrics and Patent Analysis	2006	Journal Article	Elsevier
[13]	Porter, A. L.; Cunningham, S. W.	Tech Mining: Exploiting New Technologies for Competitive Advantage	2005	Book	Wiley
[14]	Yoon, B.; Park, Y.	A Text-Mining-Based Patent Network: Analytical Tool for High-Technology Trend	2004	Journal Article	Elsevier
[15]	Lee, S. et al.	An Approach to Discovering New Technology Opportunities: Keyword-Based Patent Map Approach	2009	Journal Article	Elsevier
Extension Publications - Complementary Framing or boundary					
[8]	Page, M. J. et al.	The PRISMA 2020 Statement: An Updated Guideline for Reporting Systematic Reviews	2021	Journal Article	BMJ
[16]	Mankins, J. C.	Technology Readiness Levels	1995	White Paper	NASA

sufficiently explicit Technology Radar perspective, or were methodologically redundant in comparison to stronger contributions.

The final corpus therefore consisted of 10 papers (see Table I), of which 8 were classified as core Technology Radar contributions and 2 as complementary framing or boundary papers. The core set was selected because these studies directly propose, operationalize, automate, evaluate, or apply a Technology Radar approach. The complementary papers were retained because they provide essential context on the broader technology intelligence process and clarify the methodological boundaries between radar-based and alternative approaches. This distinction ensures both conceptual completeness and analytical consistency.

To synthesize the selected studies, a comparative framework was applied covering the following dimensions: purpose and application domain, data sources, identification mechanisms, selection logic, assessment criteria, visualization approach, stakeholder integration, automation level, update logic, as well as reported benefits and limitations. This PRISMA-inspired filtering and synthesis procedure increases transparency and reproducibility and demonstrates that Technology Radar research should be understood as a specialized sub-stream within the broader domains of technology intelligence and foresight. At the same time, the resulting corpus is sufficiently focused to enable a systematic comparison of existing approaches and to derive requirements for an AI-DAPT-specific Technology Radar framework, which are introduced in the next section.

But before entering the next section, it is noteworthy that a substantial share of the identified core contributions originates from earlier phases of research (2000–2015). This reflects the structural characteristics of the field: Technology Radar approaches are not yet a rapidly expanding standalone research domain but rather emerge as applied instruments within the broader areas of technology intelligence, foresight, and

innovation management. Consequently, many of the foundational methodological concepts—such as technology scouting, bibliometric analysis, and roadmapping—were established in earlier work and continue to underpin current implementations [7], [12]–[15].

More recent research, in contrast, focuses less on redefining the Technology Radar concept itself and more on enhancing it through data-driven and AI-supported methods, for example in the context of automated text mining, large-scale trend analysis, and machine learning-based information extraction [17]–[19]. These developments complement rather than replace the earlier conceptual foundations, which remain relevant for structuring and comparing radar approaches. Accordingly, the selected corpus prioritizes methodological clarity and conceptual completeness, while more recent contributions are integrated where they extend the analytical and technological capabilities of the radar framework.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. General framework definition

The literature synthesis provides three observable patterns for Technology Radar development:

- 1) **The field evolves from scouting and dissemination toward decision support.** Early radar approaches emphasize technology identification, filtering, and internal dissemination, whereas later work increasingly highlights strategic value creation, multi-criteria evaluation, and needs–technology matching [7], [9], [10], [12], [13].
- 2) **The field evolves from manual expert systems toward digital and AI-supported systems.** Foundational approaches rely strongly on scout networks and expert panels, while later contributions introduce digital collaboration, automated data acquisition, and scalable text- and patent-mining methods [9], [11]–[15].

- 3) **The field evolves from generic overview radars to ward context-specific radar logic.** Recent developments increasingly stress application-oriented evaluation, organizational needs, and implementation readiness instead of generic overview functions alone, which aligns with maturity-oriented perspectives such as Technology Readiness Levels [16].

From these patterns, five core requirements for a Technology Radar framework can be derived:

- 1) A formal process backbone covering identification, selection, assessment, and dissemination/update [7], [9].
- 2) A project-specific relevance model that goes beyond generic maturity by considering value, risk, and organizational needs [16].
- 3) Hybrid evidence acquisition combining scientific sources, expert judgment, and AI-supported extraction, as fully manual or fully automated approaches alone are insufficient [12]–[15].
- 4) Stakeholder-oriented communication and collaboration to capture the cognitive and organizational value of radar processes [9], [10].
- 5) An update mechanism that allows iterative review and traceability as technologies evolve over time [8].

These requirements informed the design of the AI-DAPT Technology Radar as a multi-source and continuously evolving framework for monitoring technological developments in AI-Ops and data-driven AI pipelines. The resulting methodology combines automated analysis with qualitative expert input and integrates an extended source base, an AI-supported processing pipeline, and interview-based validation to capture both long-term scientific developments and short-term industrial trends.

B. Source Base

The methodological foundation of the radar relies on the integration of two complementary source types. Scientific publications, primarily retrieved from Scopus, serve as a validated basis for identifying long-term technological developments and allow for the analysis of research dynamics over time. In parallel, industry- and practice-oriented sources, such as TechCrunch and ComputerWeekly, are incorporated via web scraping to capture current technological trends, product innovations, and practical implementations. This combination ensures a balanced perspective that reflects both academic progress and real-world technological adoption.

C. Data Processing Pipeline

The core of the methodology is a multi-stage data processing and analysis pipeline that structures the transformation from raw data to radar visualization. Such structured approaches are increasingly required, as traditional portfolio evaluation and decision-making processes are challenged by rising complexity and disruptive influences, which demand more systematic and data-driven methods for identifying and

assessing relevant technologies [20]. Subsequently, a keyword-based search is performed using large language models (OpenAI), enabling the dynamic generation and application of context-relevant search terms, which is consistent with the need for automation on literature described by [21], [22]. This step is followed by an automated filtering process, also supported by OpenAI, which removes redundancies and refines the dataset to technologically relevant content.

A scoring mechanism is then applied to evaluate identified technologies based on two complementary evidence dimensions: research trend dynamics derived from scientific publications and industry visibility derived from practice-oriented sources. Rather than relying on a single source type, both dimensions are considered jointly to capture differences between academic attention and practical adoption. The resulting relevance assessment serves as the basis for the initial classification of technologies within the radar.

Technologies are assigned to radar rings according to their observed relevance, maturity, and applicability within the project context. The *Adopt* ring contains technologies with strong evidence and direct applicability, while *Trial* represents promising technologies that have demonstrated relevance but require further evaluation. Technologies in the *Assess* ring are considered emerging and are therefore monitored for future developments, whereas *Hold* includes technologies with limited current relevance or insufficient supporting evidence.

The resulting classification is subjected to a structured review process by the project team, ensuring consistency and contextual relevance. Finally, the validated data is transformed into structured formats (e.g., JSON) and visualized using a ThoughtWorks-based open-source Technology Radar, deployed within a containerized (Docker) environment.

D. Interview-Based Validation

To complement the data-driven pipeline, qualitative insights from project partners are systematically integrated through an interview-based validation process. This approach follows principles inspired by the Delphi method [23], aiming to incorporate expert knowledge in a structured and iterative manner.

Interviews with project partners are recorded and transcribed using automated speech recognition tools with speaker attribution. These inputs are formalized into structured data representations and consolidated into an overview of proposed changes. The expert review does not replace the data-driven classification, but serves as a validation and refinement mechanism. Experts may recommend the addition of previously unidentified technologies, the reclassification of technologies between rings, or the adjustment of relevance assessments where project-specific knowledge indicates a different practical significance than suggested by the automated analysis.

The project-centric validation process consisted of nine interview sessions involving representatives from all development partners contributing to the AI-DAPT platform. Depending on the breadth of partner responsibilities, between one and three participants joined each session to ensure that all relevant

technical viewpoints were represented. The objective was not to obtain statistically representative samples but to capture the complete range of perspectives from the organizations responsible for developing the project’s technological components.

To consolidate potentially differing assessments, proposed classifications and relevance ratings were aggregated using a majority-vote principle and mean-value calculation where ordinal evaluations were provided. This procedure ensured consistent treatment of differing viewpoints while maintaining traceability of the resulting classifications.

E. Iterative Methodological Framework

The overall methodology follows an iterative framework, allowing for continuous refinement and adaptation. In regular update cycles, new data sources are incorporated, keyword strategies are adjusted, scoring mechanisms are recalibrated, and results are validated by the project team. This iterative process ensures that the radar remains up-to-date and responsive to emerging technological developments while maintaining methodological consistency.

In this way, the AI-DAPT Technology Radar establishes a structured approach that combines automated data analysis with expert-driven validation, enabling a robust and adaptable representation of the evolving technology landscape.

IV. RESULTS

This section reports the main outcomes of the implemented Technology Radar, including source integration effects, technology structuring, expert-based refinements, and the deployed radar artifact. The outcomes demonstrate both methodological advancements and substantive insights into the technology landscape of AI-Ops and data-driven pipelines as a specific instantiation of the AI-DAPT project.

TABLE II
QUANTITATIVE RESULTS OF THE AI-DAPT TECHNOLOGY RADAR
FRAMEWORK

Technology Radar Metrics	Value
Interview sessions conducted	9
Technologies identified in final radar	127
Technologies added through expert validation	49
Technologies reclassified through expert validation	51
Technologies removed	0
Radar quadrants	4
Radar maturity rings	4

As shown in Table II, the implemented framework produced a publicly available Technology Radar containing 127 technologies distributed across four thematic quadrants and four maturity rings. Beyond the automated identification process, expert validation had a substantial influence on the final outcome. Across nine interview sessions, 49 technologies were added and 51 technologies were reclassified, demonstrating the complementary value of project-specific expertise alongside the data-driven evidence base.

For completeness, the underlying literature review identified 39 records, reduced them to 19 full-text assessments, and synthesized a final corpus of 10 publications (see Section II).

A. Integrated Source Perspective

The combination of scientific publications and industry-oriented sources enabled a differentiated view on technological developments. Publications indexed in Scopus (available via API) provided a stable basis for identifying sustained research activity and longitudinal trends, while web-based sources such as TechCrunch and ComputerWeekly reflected short-term dynamics, including emerging tools, product announcements, and shifts in industrial practice. This dual perspective revealed systematic differences between research-driven and practice-driven developments. Several technologies exhibited lasting scientific relevance, whereas others showed substantial adoption in industry-oriented sources despite comparatively low representation in the scientific literature reflecting the rapid pace of AI-related innovation. This confirms the value of combining both evidence dimensions within a single radar framework.

B. Pipeline Performance and Automation Effects

The developed pipeline operationalizes the full workflow that combines research trend dynamics with industry visibility. Compared to earlier approaches, the pipeline significantly reduces manual intervention while improving consistency [22].

Automated keyword expansion increased the coverage of relevant publications and articles, while AI-supported filtering reduced redundancy and enhanced topical precision. The scoring mechanism - based on number of articles, currentness/momentum, strategic relevance - enabled a consistent prioritization across heterogeneous sources, resulting in a reproducible classification of technologies. The final output, generated as structured JSON files and deployed via a ThoughtWorks-inspired radar framework, provides an interactive and coherent representation of the identified technology landscape.

C. Technology Identification and Structuring

The application of the scoring and classification logic led to the identification of distinct technology clusters within the domains of AI-Ops and data-driven pipelines. These clusters reflect varying levels of maturity, adoption, and innovation dynamics (consistent with findings reported in [7]). The analysis indicates the presence of established technologies with strong representation in both scientific and industrial sources, alongside emerging technologies that are gaining industrial relevance but are not yet extensively covered in academic literature. In addition, research-intensive topics were identified that exhibit high publication activity while remaining in early stages of industrial application.

The radar structure enables a clear differentiation between these categories and supports a structured interpretation of technological maturity and relevance.

D. Contribution of Interview-Based Review

The integration of partner interviews introduced a qualitative validation layer to the predominantly data-driven approach. Following a structured procedure inspired by Delphi-

like principles, expert feedback was systematically captured, transcribed, and translated into structured change proposals.

The interview process had a measurable impact on the resulting radar. Across the nine interview sessions, experts proposed 49 technologies that were subsequently added to the radar and contributed to the identification of project-specific developments that were not sufficiently visible in the analyzed source base. In addition, 51 technologies were reclassified with respect to their radar positioning based on consolidated expert assessments. While no technologies were removed entirely, the review process substantially improved the contextualization and prioritization of technologies from an AI-DAPT perspective.

This process contributed to a refinement of technology positioning within the radar, enabled the identification of domain-specific technologies not sufficiently represented in the analyzed data sources, and supported adjustments of relevance assessments based on practical experience. As a result, the overall contextual accuracy of the radar was improved and better aligned with real-world application scenarios, particularly with regard to actively used technologies within the project environment. Generally a Technology Radar represents opinionated viewpoint onto a certain area [6]. Consequently, the radar reflects an AI-DAPT-specific perspective that incorporates expert knowledge from partners directly involved in the development of project technologies.

E. Publication and Accessibility of the Technology Radar

To ensure transparency, accessibility, and practical usability, the resulting Technology Radar is publicly deployed via the project website. The radar visualization is generated from the final JSON artifacts produced by the pipeline and rendered using a ThoughtWorks-inspired framework. This approach follows established practices of Technology Radar visualization as popularized by ThoughtWorks [6], enabling users to interactively explore identified technologies, their classifications, and their relative positioning. The current version of the radar is publicly accessible via the project platform¹, thereby enabling continuous dissemination and validation of results beyond the scope of this publication.

Figure 2 illustrates the end-to-end workflow of the implemented system. It depicts the integration of heterogeneous data sources, including scientific publications and web-based inputs, the application of AI-based keyword generation and filtering, and the subsequent scoring and classification process. The final stage highlights the transformation of processed data into a radar visualization, which is deployed in a web-based environment.

The published Technology Radar is implemented as an interactive web-based visualization following the established quadrant–ring structure. It organizes the identified technologies into four thematic quadrants (Techniques, Platforms, Tools, and Languages & Frameworks) and four maturity levels (Adopt, Trial, Assess, Hold). In its current version, the

Fig. 2. Overview of the AI-assisted Technology Radar pipeline, from data acquisition and processing to final deployed and web-based visualization

radar comprises a total of 127 technologies, with a relatively balanced distribution across quadrants and a concentration of entries in the Adopt and Trial rings. For example, the “Languages & Frameworks” quadrant alone contains over 35 technologies, including widely adopted tools such as Python, PyTorch, and TensorFlow, while the “Techniques” quadrant reflects a broader spread across maturity stages, from established methods (e.g., CNNs) to emerging approaches (e.g., retrieval-augmented generation). The visualization further distinguishes between newly added and previously existing entries, enabling a dynamic representation of technological evolution. This structured layout allows users to explore the technology landscape along both functional and maturity dimensions in a scalable and interpretable manner.

F. Evaluation of Alternative Approaches

During the development process, several alternative methods were explored but ultimately discarded due to limited reliability or insufficient added value. Approaches based solely on direct Scopus-derived scoring did not provide a sufficiently balanced view, while manual keyword generation and filtering proved to be inefficient and less consistent. The integration of external trend indicators, including platforms such as Google Trends, Stack Overflow Trends, and Wikipedia-based metrics, did not yield stable or reproducible insights. Similarly, evaluations based on general-purpose search engine results and the inclusion of additional web sources with restricted access or

¹<https://techradar.ai-dapt.eu/>

narrow thematic focus did not contribute meaningfully to the analysis.

These findings underline the necessity of the chosen hybrid methodology, which combines curated scientific data, industry-oriented sources, and AI-supported processing.

Overall, the results indicate that the framework can support semi-automated technology identification while combining scientific, industry-oriented, and expert-based inputs.

V. DISCUSSION

The presented Technology Radar and its underlying framework demonstrate a comprehensive and forward-looking approach to monitoring and structuring technological developments in the domain of AI-Ops and data-driven pipelines. From a practical perspective, the integration of heterogeneous data sources, combined with an AI-assisted processing pipeline, represents a significant advancement compared to traditional, largely manual technology scouting approaches. The ability to systematically combine long-term scientific developments with short-term industrial signals enables a more balanced and nuanced understanding of the technological landscape. In particular, the hybridization of automated analysis with expert-based validation through interviews enhances the contextual relevance of the results and mitigates the limitations of purely data-driven methods. This combination allows not only for scalability and efficiency but also for the inclusion of domain-specific knowledge that would otherwise remain implicit or inaccessible.

A. Answering Research Question(s)

The central research question is derived from the objective of Section I, which can be phrased: *How can a project-driven Technology Radar framework be systematically developed that combines scientific evidence, industry-oriented information sources, AI-supported processing, and expert validation to support technology monitoring and decision-making?*

A balanced view emerges when considering both the strengths and limitations of the approach. The framework successfully establishes a robust foundation for semi-automated technology monitoring by combining scalability with contextual depth. At the same time, its effectiveness depends on careful calibration, continuous validation, and the thoughtful integration of additional data sources. The hybrid approach, which merges automated data processing with expert knowledge, proves to be a key enabler for achieving this balance, as it allows the system to leverage both quantitative signals and qualitative insights.

B. Match and Contribution

The literature review was intentionally focused on identifying design-relevant Technology Radar approaches rather than conducting a broad bibliometric analysis of technology intelligence research. Consequently, the review serves primarily as a structured foundation for framework derivation, while the main contribution of the paper lies in the development and implementation of the AI-DAPT Technology

Radar framework. From a theoretical perspective, the work contributes a synthesized framework that combines concepts from Technology Radar research, technology intelligence, corporate foresight, and AI-assisted information processing into a coherent and operationalizable approach for project-level technology monitoring.

Overall, the presented approach constitutes a flexible and extensible foundation for Technology Radar development. Its ability to combine automated analysis with expert-driven refinement positions it as a valuable instrument for both research and practice, while also highlighting the importance of continuous methodological evolution to address increasing complexity and emerging data sources. Beyond technology monitoring itself, the framework supports engineering and innovation management activities such as technology prioritization, roadmap development, portfolio assessment, and strategic decision-making in rapidly evolving technological environments.

Beyond the immediate application context, the approach exhibits considerable potential for transferability [1]. The modular pipeline architecture and the generalizable structure of the radar suggest applicability across various domains that are characterized by rapid technological change and heterogeneous information sources. This includes fields such as smart manufacturing, energy systems, healthcare technologies, and industrial IoT ecosystems. In such environments, where both academic research and industrial innovation evolve in parallel but often asynchronously, the presented framework can support technology assessment and evidence-based decision-making. The iterative design further contributes to the long-term effectiveness of the approach, as it allows continuous adaptation to new data sources, evolving terminology, and shifting technological priorities.

This paper directly addresses the ICE2026 Technology topic TEC 1: *Artificial Intelligence for Technology Management*, and is therefore closely aligned with Special Track ST01, which is dedicated to the same thematic focus. It further aligns with the broader IEEE TEMS orientation and research objectives concerning the management of emerging technologies, practical frameworks, implementation challenges, and value creation.

VI. CONCLUSION

The following section summarizes the main insights of the study, reflects on its limitations, and outlines perspectives for future refinement and application of the proposed approach.

A. Limitations

However, a critical perspective reveals several limitations and constraints that affect both the current implementation and its broader applicability. The effectiveness of the framework is closely linked to the availability, accessibility, and quality of its underlying data sources. While the integration of scientific publications and selected web sources provides a solid foundation, the exclusion of additional evidence sources such as patents, standards, and international initiatives remains a notable limitation, as these often contain early indicators of

technological change and strategic direction. Their integration, however, introduces substantial complexity in terms of data acquisition, normalization, and interpretation and has therefore not yet been realized in an automated and scalable manner. In addition, the framework relies on model-driven processing and AI-based filtering mechanisms, which, despite improving keyword generation and content selection, may introduce biases or inconsistencies depending on source quality, prompt design, and model behavior. The scoring mechanism, while systematic, is further based on assumptions regarding the relative importance of scientific and industry-oriented signals, which may not be equally valid across different domains. Finally, the expert-based validation process, although valuable for contextualization and refinement, introduces a degree of subjectivity that can influence the final positioning of technologies within the radar. These limitations indicate that Technology Radar development remains an evolving challenge that requires continuous methodological refinement.

Transferability is therefore not without constraints. The framework is particularly well-suited for domains with a strong digital footprint and a high availability of structured and semi-structured data. In contrast, domains with limited public data, highly specialized knowledge bases, or low publication activity may not benefit to the same extent from the automated components of the approach. Additionally, the effort required to adapt keyword strategies, scoring mechanisms, and source selection to new domains should not be underestimated, as these elements are critical to the quality of the results.

B. Concluding Remarks

This paper presented the design and implementation of a Technology Radar framework developed within the context of the AI-DAPT project. Building on a structured literature review and a PRISMA-inspired methodology, the work derives a set of requirements that reflect current developments in technology intelligence, including the shift toward data-driven, context-aware, and continuously evolving approaches.

The proposed framework combines heterogeneous data sources with an AI-assisted processing pipeline and integrates qualitative expert knowledge through an interview-based validation process. This hybrid approach enables the identification and structuring of both long-term scientific developments and short-term industrial trends, resulting in a balanced and scalable technology monitoring instrument. The implementation demonstrates that the combination of automated analysis and expert input, which was set upon foundations of [5], [23], can significantly improve both efficiency and contextual relevance compared to traditional approaches.

Overall, the presented framework contributes to the systematization of Technology Radar design and provides a transferable foundation for application in other domains characterized by rapid technological change.

C. Future Work/Perspectives

Future work should focus on extending the framework's source base and improving its adaptability to different ap-

plication domains. A primary direction involves the systematic integration of additional evidence sources, particularly patents, standardization activities, and international research and innovation initiatives, which can provide early indicators of technological change and strategic developments [1]. In addition, domain-dependent source selection strategies should be investigated. While ComputerWeekly and TechCrunch were selected in the present study due to their visibility, circulation, and continuous coverage of digital technologies, other application domains may require different source portfolios. Future Technology Radar implementations should therefore support the dynamic integration and evaluation of source types that best reflect the technological characteristics of the respective domain.

A second area of future work concerns methodological refinement. This includes the development of systematic approaches for deriving application- and problem-oriented radar quadrants, which currently follow concepts established by Thoughtworks [6] and adopted in various practical implementations such as the Technology Trend Radar of BMW [24] and the Technology Radar of ETSI [25]. Furthermore, refinements of scoring mechanisms, bias detection in AI-supported processing steps, and the deeper formalization of expert integration processes could improve the robustness, transparency, and reproducibility of radar generation. In particular, more structured Delphi-inspired procedures may support iterative consensus building while reducing subjectivity in technology assessments.

Finally, the presented framework is based on the assumption that a hybrid, semi-automated approach can balance the strengths of manual expert-driven and fully automated Technology Radar generation. While manual approaches provide rich contextual understanding, they may become difficult to scale in rapidly evolving technology domains. On the other hand, fully automated approaches can process large volumes of information but may be affected by source bias, concept drift, and limited contextual interpretation. A systematic comparison of manual, hybrid, and fully automated radar development approaches therefore represents an important long-term research question. Such studies could provide a stronger empirical basis for evaluating scalability, robustness, transferability, and decision-support quality across different application domains.

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